

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

*ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal*

№3

2025
MART

Google Scholar

OPEN ACCESS

ULRICHSWEB™
GLOBAL SERIALS DIRECTORY

Academic Resource Index
ResearchBib

ISSN INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CYBERLENINKA

OpenAIRE

ROAD

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

BASE

Crossref

НАУЧНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ
БИБЛИОТЕКА
LIBRARY.RU

РЭУ.РФ
РОССИЙСКИЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

*Elektron nashr,
42 sahifa, mart, 2025-yil.*

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Shakarov Zafar G'afforovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, PhD

TAHRIR HAY'ATI:

Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor, akademik
Sharipov Kongratbay Avazimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor
Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor
Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Bo'taboyev Mahammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor, TDIU kengash kotibi
Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent
Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Sharipov Botirali Roxataliyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dots.nt
Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD
Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

MUHANDISLIK & IQTISODIYOT

*ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal*

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikasiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikasiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil
28-avgustdagi 360/5-son
qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar
asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop
etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy
ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga
texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari
bo'yicha "Muhandislik va
iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga
kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

1. Toshkent shahridagi G. V. Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
2. Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
3. Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
4. Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
5. Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
6. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
7. Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

Kapital bozori orqali tijorat banklari investitsion jozibadorligini oshirishning o'ziga xos jihatlari	10
Azimjon Abdiraxmonov	
Chuqur muruntov kareri misolida geodinamik monitoring tizimini tashkil etish va bortlarning barqarorligini bashorat qilish	16
SH.SH. Zairov, SH.T. Tadjiyev, S.A. Saydullayeva	
Paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlarining innovatsion faoliyatini tashkil etish yo'llari.....	22
Tojiyev Sa'dulla Muhitdinovich	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklari faoliyatida aktivlar daromadliligini oshirish masalalari.....	30
Saxibjonov Muzaffar Salijanovich	
Econometric modeling of bank liabilities	36
Muminova Parvina Ilhomovna	

ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF BANK LIABILITIES

Muminova Parvina Ilhomovna

Tashkent State University of Economy
Basic doctoral student(PhD) of the
“Bank accounting and audit” department
ORCID 0009-00067879-8800

Abstract: In this article, the interaction of deposit operations offered to the population in all commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan on the bank's financial condition is analyzed in econometric models.

Keywords: commercial banks, deposit operations, savings deposit, demand deposits, term deposits, net profit, interest expense, logarithmic model, econometric modeling, Brosch Pogan test, Log likelihood, Akaike, Bayeseian.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasidagi barcha tijorat banklarida aholi uchun taklif qilinadigan depozit operatsiyalarining bank moliyaviy holatiga ta'siri ekonometrik modellar asosida tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: tijorat banklari, depozit operatsiyalari, jamg'arma depoziti, talab qilinadigan depozitlar, muddatli depozitlar, sof foyda, foiz xarajatlari, logaritmik model, ekonometrik modellashtirish, Brosch Pogan testi, Log likelihood, Akaike, Bayesiy.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется влияние депозитных операций, предлагаемых населению во всех коммерческих банках Республики Узбекистан, на финансовое состояние банков с использованием эконометрических моделей.

Ключевые слова: коммерческие банки, депозитные операции, сберегательный депозит, депозиты до востребования, срочные депозиты, чистая прибыль, процентные расходы, логарифмическая модель, эконометрическое моделирование, тест Броша-Погана, Log likelihood, Акаике, Байесовский.

INTRODUCTION

One of the main areas of improvement in financial control is the application of international standards of accounting and auditing to this process. As a result of the categorization of accounts that take into account the costs of settlement operations shown to customers in banks sources of financing, types of activities, directions, and places of occurrence of costs their items are adapted to the requirements of national and international standards of accounting and control.

If we study and analyze the period from the origin of banks to the present day, we can see that the concepts of savings and deposits appeared as soon as the first banks emerged. The existence of both the wealthy and the less affluent has always been a fundamental aspect of society. It would not be incorrect to state that the demand of money holders to place their surplus funds in a secure location laid the foundation for the concept of deposits.

It is well known that the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with changes in money circulation and economic growth in the country, directly depends on the activities of commercial banks in this region. As the operations of commercial banks expand and efficiency indicators improve, the banking system strengthens, money aggregates are distributed appropriately, the money supply is regulated effectively, and, simultaneously, economic growth accelerates.

In particular, when analyzing the development of the banking system in Uzbekistan within the segment of commercial banks, we can assess the extent to which economic indicators have been established. [1]

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

First of all, the accounting daily balance for the last recorded date is required, and a comprehensive analysis of the daily balance is conducted as necessary. Afterward, the compatibility of synthetic (cumulative) and analytical (spread) calculations is verified step by step through direct comparison.

Additionally, this section outlines the procedure for opening accounts and sub-accounts for customers, ensuring the proper formalization and completeness of their legal documents. It also examines the timely and accurate registration of opened and closed accounts in the 61-form book, the completion of legally binding service contracts with customers, the correct calculation and collection of service fees, and the formalization and acceptance of daily documents for proper transfer. The establishment of final control within the department is carried out based on the relevant guidelines. [3]

Verification of settlement transactions provided to customers in banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan is conducted in accordance with the instructions of the Central Bank (№ 1831, 1948, 3229), the "Accounting Plan of Accounts in Commercial Banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan," and its amendments, along with other regulatory documents issued by the Central Bank. [2]

The audit process begins by assessing the operational efficiency of the accounting department. It involves verifying the existence of a structured work plan, evaluating the proper distribution of tasks among employees, ensuring their access to the necessary manuals, and determining their level of knowledge regarding the relevant regulations. During the audit, analytical and synthetic account balances are compared across all balance accounts for a specific day designated by the head of the audit. [4]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is based on scientific methodologies such as dialectics, logic, analysis and synthesis, and a comprehensive approach.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The comparison of the analytical account with the synthetic account for the bank's internal accounts is conducted based on equipment sheets and books, which serve as the foundation for the analytical account. This process involves reconciling the open amounts recorded in the books with the corresponding amounts listed in these sheets. Transaction books or synthetic personal accounts are verified by matching each open amount recorded under the balance sheet account, with the final balance being confirmed based on the issued balance for the account.

The legitimacy of fund transfers from open-ended deposit accounts, loans, and other accounts which are not covered in other sections of the audit can be examined through document verification and personal account analysis, following the scope determined by the head of the audit. In this case, special attention must be given to orders for the purchase of material goods, particularly transactions authorized by officials who do not provide services to the respective client. Additionally, it is crucial to ensure that all related documents are correctly executed and comply with applicable regulations.

Soffoyda	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
jamgarma	-.8726428	.6534433	-1.34	0.189	-2.189571	.4442856
talabqo	-.0875734	.2802514	-0.31	0.756	-.652383	.4772361
muddatli	.5341338	.2263257	2.36	0.023	.0780043	.9902632
_cons	4561.951	3066.379	1.49	0.144	-1617.929	10741.83

Figure 1. Analysis of the relationship between deposits and net profit of commercial banks.

$$Y = -0.87 - 0.08x_1 + 0.53x_2 + 4561.95$$

In this

Y = net profit

x₁ = savings deposit

x₂ = deposit funds until demand

x₃ = term deposits

Our regression analysis shows that the total deposit operations of commercial banks are a passive operation of the banking system, i.e. bank liabilities, which indirectly affect the bank's profit. It can be seen that, based on the results of the analysis, we found out that the total term deposits of commercial banks have an indirect effect on the increase in bank profits.

Modeling the relationship between the net profit of commercial banks and total types of deposits

	1-model	2-model	3-model	4-model
Net profit	*			*
Time deposits	0.24		0.00005	
In net profit		*	*	
In time deposits		0.88		3725.27
F-test	41.16	24.46	24.58	35.12
	0.47	0.35	0.35	0.43
Adj	0.46	0.33	0.33	0.42
Root MSE	2104.2	0.62	0.62	2181.1
Brosch Pogan test	5.0 Prob>chi2_ 0.02	0.41 Prob>chi2_ 0.52	1.01 Prob>chi2_ 0.31	7.22 Prob>chi2_ 0.0072
Durbin Watson test	0.69	0.80	0.81	0.64

If we analyze our models of 4 different methods presented in the table above, the most reliable is the 2nd model, that is, the logarithmic model, according to which, if the balance of fixed deposits of commercial banks increases by 1%, the net profit of commercial banks increases by 0.88% indirectly leads to an increase.

Continuing this research, we will consider the relationship between the deposit operations offered to the population in commercial banks and the total interest costs of commercial banks in one of the econometric models.

Table 2. Analysis of interest costs of commercial banks in ARIMA tests.

Mezonlar	A ARIMA(2,1,0)	B ARIMA(2,1,1)	C ARIMA(2,1,2)	D ARIMA(1,1,0)	E ARIMA(1,1,1)	Optimal
Parametrlar	3/0	3/0	3/0	3/0	3/0	
Sigma	0.66	0.61	-0.32	0.68	0.67	C
Log likelihood	-46.74	-43.91	-46.20	-47.84	-47.02	B
Akaike	103.49	97.82	106.40	103.67	104.05	B
Bayeseian	112.63	106.96	119.20	110.99	113.19	B

Through this econometric analysis, we have tested various tests to reduce the interest costs of commercial banks to the ARIMA model. In particular, as a result of conducting log likelihood, Akaike and Bayesian tests, we accepted option B as it fully meets all standards from options A, B, C, D and E.

The auditor verifies that the application is submitted along with the register, ensuring that the first copy of the register is signed by the head and chief accountant of the enterprise, stamped, and that all required indicators are accurate. If the service is provided by a single bank, the application is prepared in three copies:

- The first and second copies remain at the bank until payment is processed.
- The third copy is provided to the Payer for acknowledgment, no later than the next working day, with the document receipt date indicated.

The auditor also checks whether a copy of the application is attached to the bank's daily collection of documents, along with the extract from the recipient's personal account.

Based on our analysis, we determined that savings deposits are the primary factor contributing to the increase in interest costs for commercial banks, while term deposit operations have the lowest impact, accounting for 26% of the increase in costs.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

To sum up, one of the key areas for improving financial control in banks is the application of international accounting and state auditing standards. This process involves the classification of accounts based on the costs of banking operations, sources of financing, types of activities, areas of expenditure, and cost-incurring locations. Additionally, it facilitates the harmonization of national and international standards.

In this regard, it is recommended that banks adopt international accounting standards comprehensively and implement a structured system of accounts that reflects the costs of settlement operations in commercial banks.

Based on our general analysis, we conclude that an increase in the volume of term deposit operations in commercial banks can indirectly enhance profitability while also contributing to a reduction in interest expenses.

List of used literature

1. "On Requirements for Internal Audit of Commercial Banks" № 3302. Regulation. April 16, 2021.
2. "On the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan" (new edition). November 11, 2019.
3. "On Banks and Banking Activities" (new version). November 5, 2019.
4. Umarov, Z. A., & Muminova, P. I. Tijorat banklarida depozit operatsiyalari auditing nazariy asoslari hamda yuritilish tartibi. // International Conferences. – 2022. – Vol. 1, No. 1. – P. 50-54.

5. Muminov, Z. Sh., Muminova, P. I., & Mekhmonov, S. Byudjet tashkilotlarida xarajatlar hisobi va ichki nazoratini takomillashtirish. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(1), 40–46, 2022.
6. Muminova, P. I., & Umarov, Z. A. Banklarda mijozlarga ko'rsatiladigan hisob-kitob operatsiyalari auditi. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(1), 113–124, 2022.
7. Sayitkulova, P. I., & Avlokulov, A. Z. The International Audit Standards and Composition of the Audit, as well as the Importance of Tax Accounting. *Materials of the Conference: International Accounting and Audit Standards: Practical Application in the Digital Economy*, 26-29, 2020.
8. State Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Official portal: www.gov.uz
9. Press Service of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Official website: www.press-service.uz
10. Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Official website: www.cbu.uz
11. Economic Research Center. Official website: www.cer.uz

MUHANDISLIK & IQTISODIYOT

*ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal*

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 3

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

t.me/yait_2100